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Knowing the Albanian “hurma” (*Diospyros kaki Thunb.*) fruit and its drying behaviour based on quality characteristics and bioactive compounds

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Abstract - The study aims to investigate main physico-chemical parameters, polyphenols and antioxidant potential of Albanian hurma (*Diospyros kaki Thunb.*) in fresh and dried state. The study was conducted during 2020-2021, and samples were collected randomly by trees over 40 years, in full maturity stage, from Tirana, Durres, and Elbasan regions in the central part of Albania, which are recognized traditionally for hurma fruits growing. Drying regimes used in a laboratory scale hot-air dehydrator: temperature $60 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ and air velocity 1 ± 0.1 m/s, relative humidity approximately 40% (at the beginning) and 10% (at the end). The independent variables specified in the experimental design were region of cultivation, and the physico-chemical parameters determined for fresh and dried fruits were: dry matter, total soluble solids (TSS), total acidity, pH, total ash, vitamin C, colour values (L^* , a^* , b^*), water activity (a_w). As well were determined total polyphenols, flavonoids, and antioxidant potential. Drying hurma resulted in a change of all parameters, resulting in an increase of dry matter over 3-fold, total acidity 0.154-0.192 g/100 g increased over 2-fold, pH from 6.6 decreased to 4.6, vitamin C was in a low amount of 7.22-7.74 mg/ 100 g and lost all content after drying, a_w 0.929-0.938, was decreased after drying 0.74-0.75. The antioxidant activity in fresh and in dried hurma fruit ranged 37.9-39.3 and 78.2-80.7 ascorbic acid equivalent/100 g, the total polyphenolic ranged 74.2-93.3 and 101.7-125.2 mg gallic acid equivalent/100 g, flavonoid content 21.1-37.8 and 76.7-98.9 mg catechin equivalent/100 g. There is a strong influence of growing region for hurma based on the observed quality parameters for fresh and dried fruits, where those cultivated in Elbasan region had the best quality. This study may serve as basis for selecting hurma varieties, for further development and prospect in fruit growing sector and with potential for diversification by food industry into new products.

Keywords - antioxidant potential, drying, persimmon, physico-chemical characteristics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Persimmon (*Diospyros kaki Thunb.*) is a member of the Ebenaceae family, native of East Asian countries and growing in some Mediterranean countries (Izuchi, 2011). In Albania this fruit is known as “hurma” and exist in a number of cultivars, grown and produced in our country for more than

100 years. Persimmon is a seasonal fruit, which can be purchased from September to early December (Toplu, 2009). It is s mainly eaten fresh, but can be frozen, canned, sometimes used in culinary, also other preservation methods to offer long-term and safe way of storage (de Ancos, 2000). Drying of persimmons has been used traditionally to obtain a product with good sensory attributes as well as storage stability (Park et al. 2006). Persimmon has a quite good nutritional value: it contains many compounds such as different sugars, starch, organic acids and amino acids, proanthocyanidins, flavonoids, carotenoids, triterpenoids and fatty acids (Veberic, et al. 2010; Zhou et al. 2010; da Conceição Santos et al. 2018), proteins, and vitamins A, B₆, B₁₂, C, and D (Kim, et al., 2013). The colour of the fruit is attributed to the carotenoid pigments in the pericarp and the content of lycopene (dark orange) is related with the autumn daylight conditions. Due to its richness in phenolic compounds, vitamin C, and carotenoids, persimmon has a strong antioxidant activity (Jung et al. 2005). In general, microbiological, physicochemical, and sensory properties are considered for determining the shelf-life and quality of foods (MFDS, 2011). Major quality parameters associated with dried foods are the changes in color, visual appearance, microbial population abundance, texture, nutrients, and water activity (Carcel et al. 2010). However, the quality parameters for determining the shelf-life and quality of dried foods have not been intensively investigated so far in persimmons. The study aims to investigate main physico-chemical parameters, polyphenols and antioxidant potential of Albanian hurma (*Diospyros kaki Thunb.*), fresh and dried fruits.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Diospyros kaki Thunb. was collected during 2021, picked up randomly by trees over 40 years, in full maturity stage, from Tirana, Durres, and Elbasan regions in the central part of Albania, which are recognised traditionally for hurma fruits growing. Fruits were transported immediately to the laboratory for further analysis and drying. Fruits were pre-

selected with uniform maturity, shape, size, colour, and free from defects. For drying hurma fruits, a laboratory scale hot-air dehydrator was used, and the drying chamber consisted of a centrifugal air blower (horizontally across the ten trays), electrical heating elements, with adjustable temperature here applied $60 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ and air velocity 1 ± 0.1 m/s, relative humidity approximately 40% (at the beginning) and 10% (at the end), (Hoxha and Kongoli, 2016). Hurma fruits were cut in slices of 3 mm and set on thin layer, and the drying process last approximately 6 h. Samples were coded with symbols K: kaki (synonym name of hurma), F: fresh, D: dried, accompanied with their origin region -T: Tirana, -D: Durres and -E: Elbasan, respectively: KF-T, KD-T, KF-E, KD-E, KF-D, and KD-D. Dry matter, water activity (a_w), total ash, total soluble solids (TSS), ratio TSS/TA, total acidity (TA), pH, colour values (L^* , a^* , b^*), as well as vitamin C, total polyphenols, flavonoids, and antioxidant potential were determined according to Hoxha and Kongoli (2021). The fruit extracts prepared based on solid-liquid extraction with 60% aqueous methanol adapted according to method Hoxha et al. (2021). where 1 (± 0.001) g of fruits was extracted by using 10 ml of methanol 60 % (solvent/water; v/v), and 1% HCl_{cc} , vortex for 1 min, assisted with ultrasound for 15 min (40 KHz), centrifugated at 3500 rpm for 5 min, filtration, and finally the supernatant collected. All measurements were done in triplicate, and calculated as mean values \pm SD.

III. RESULTS

The dry matter ranged between 22.98-76.85g/100g fw. (in fresh weight basis of sample), total ash 0.423-0.883 g/100 g fw., a_w ranged 0.938 to 0.737 (Figure 1.).

Figure 1. Dry matter (%) and water activity in fresh and dried hurma

TSS values resulted 19 to 21°Brix where main component of this fruit is a saccharide comprising glucose and fructose, and the ratio of TSS/TA was 98.95-136.71 (Figure 2.).

Figure 2. Total soluble solids (TSS) and the ratio of TSS/total acidity in fresh hurma

Total acidity resulted 0.154 to 0.422 g/100 g fw. Where the main organic acids ones in persimmon being malic and citric acids (Ryu et al. 2016); and pH values 4.6 to 6.6 (Figure 3.).

Figure 3. Total acidity and pH values of fresh and dried hurma

Persimmon is a spherical fruit with a colour that ranges from reddish to yellow according to carotene content, the pulp is a viscous orange-red and somewhat rough, depending on the content of tannins. The pulp, regardless of the variety, consists mainly of mucilage and pectin, which is responsible for its characteristic appearance (OMAIAA, 2021). Fresh hurma colour values resulted for L^* , a^* , b^* respectively 65.73-71.82, 10.82-13.63, 35.27-39.81 (Figure 4.).

Figure 4. Colour values (L^* , a^* , b^*) of fresh and dried hurma

Figure 5. The content of total polyphenols (TP), total flavonoid (TF) and antioxidant activity (TAA) in fresh hurma fruits

Figure 6. The content of total polyphenols (TP), total flavonoid (TF) and antioxidant activity (TAA) in dried hurma fruits

Total vitamin C was in a low amount of 7.22-7.74 mg/100 g fw., about 2/3 of the total amount is available as L-ascorbic acid (Giordani et al. 2011), and the broad variations of its content can be explained through environmental factors, fruit's inherent qualities, time of harvest, and the general conditions of the crop (Direito et al. 2019). The total polyphenolic ranged 74.2-93.3 and 101.7-125.2 mg gallic acid equivalent/100 g fw., flavonoid content 21.1-37.8 and 76.7-98.9 mg catechin equivalent/100 g fw. (catechins (flavan-3-ol) are the main flavonoids found in persimmons, and the antioxidant activity in fresh and in dried hurma fruit ranged 37.9-39.3 and 78.2-80.7 ascorbic acid equivalent/100 g fw. (Figures 5. and 6.).

IV. DISCUSSION

Fresh hurma fruits showed slight differences in values of parameters, where variety E had highest values for dry matter, total ash, TSS, TSS/TA ratio, pH and Vit C, and

lowest for TA, and variety T had the lowest values compared to E and D hurma varieties, whereas variety D showed intermediate values. These values are within the range of other studies (Ozen et al. 2004; Ercisli et al. 2008). Drying hurma resulted in a change of all parameters, resulting in an increase of dry matter over 3-fold, a_w was decreased after drying 0.74-0.75, total ash and total acidity increased over 2-fold, pH from 6.6 decreased to 4.6, vitamin C lost all the content after drying, while bioactive compounds have increased over 1.3 to 3 folds. Hurma fruit colour values resulted for L^* , a^* , b^* after drying no big differences occurred for L^* and b^* , but a^* increased from 16.55 to 18.78. Colour values, water activity, retention of nutrients can be used as factors for determining the shelf-life of dried persimmons, however further studies investigating other quality parameters such as visual appearance, texture, microbial load, and chemical stability to determine the shelf-life of dried foods need to be conducted. Total phenolic content in persimmons as reported by available literature differed extensively (Veberic et al. 2010; Jang et al. 2010) in general resulted that persimmon has higher content of total phenolic compounds when compared to grapes, apple and tomato (Chen et al., 2008). Hurma collected from different locations (Tirana, Durres and Elbasan), shown the influence of growing location on the observed quality parameters for fresh and dried fruits. Hurma cultivated in Elbasan region resulted with best quality, followed by Durres with intermediate quality compared to hurma grown in Tirana.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Albanian hurma fruits beside providing nutrients such as minerals, vitamins, phytochemicals, may serve as good source of natural antioxidants sources, and may be utilised in reformulating and improving food products quality, even as natural colorant, etc. The drying influence of on the quality parameters resulted quite important, as occurred an increase over 3-fold in the dry matter. a_w was decreased after drying 0.74-0.75, total ash and total acidity increased over 2-fold. Furthermore, drying influenced the bioactive compounds content, which were increased over 1.3 to 3 folds. The growing locations identified as independent variable had a strong influence on the quality parameters observed for fresh and dried hurma, where those cultivated in Elbasan region resulted with the best quality, followed by hurma grown in Durres and Tirana region. This study may serve as basis for selecting Albanian hurma varieties, for further development and prospect in fruit growing sector and with potential for diversification by food industry into new products.

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